

**THE ROLE OF YOUNG PEOPLE IN CREATING A NEW
ENLIGHTENED SOCIETY OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Abstract: This article talks about how important the role of youth is in creating a new enlightened society of Uzbekistan, and also how great a blessing our independence is.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, intellectual, prosperous country, heavenly country, democratic, dreams, homeland, independence.

Uzbekistan is a paradise country. Every inch of it is sacred to us. Independent Uzbekistan is developing day by day and is among the first countries. We all know the prosperity of our country, the continuation of our independence, the intellectuality of young people in every field and their contributions.

Independence became the real owner of its destiny for our country, realized its value, created an opportunity to live a decent life, establish a legal democratic state and civil society in our country. At the moment, it is a solid ground for every person to fully demonstrate their talents and abilities in the economic and social spheres, and to realize their rights and freedoms. During the years of independence, our ancient history, rich heritage, national statehood, sacred religion, customs and traditions were revived. Today, noble qualities such as kindness, tolerance, solidarity, respect for national and universal values, the feeling of belonging to the fate and future of the Motherland have taken place from the depths of our hearts. In

fact, thanks to independence, we realized our identity, as a free people, an independent state, the opportunity was opened to show all the strength and great potential of Uzbekistan to the whole world. The world recognized us because of freedom, the selfless work of our people, the enthusiasm of our youth, with determination, the fame of our country is spreading more widely around the world. We are building our tomorrow - our free and prosperous future - with our own hands on the basis of the incomparable opportunities provided by freedom. Of course, it is natural that we consider the concepts of “independence” and “reform” as common words. Because reforms can be implemented only in an independent state and an independent society. Both independence and reforms created the necessary conditions for a person to live well and achieve a decent standard of living. As a result of the large-scale reforms carried out in our country during the years of independence, the foundation of our national statehood was strengthened, the sovereignty of our country and the inviolability of our borders were ensured, the environment of peace and tranquility, interethnic harmony and religious tolerance was strengthened in our society, the rule of law, human rights and freedoms and interests were strengthened. Great work has been done on the production. At the same time, an in-depth analysis of the development path of our country requires comprehensive consideration of the fact that today the world market is changing and competition is intensifying. requiring output and implementation.

August 31, 1991 was recorded in the annals of our history as the same honorable day. According to the historical decision made on this day, September 1 was declared Independence Day, a national holiday in our country. The main idea and main goal of our independence is to realize the age-old dreams of our people, to create suitable conditions for every citizen to live according to his dreams, to strengthen the new independent Motherland with all measures, to protect it from various attacks. was marked as In fact, there are many countries and states in the world. But for the children of this dear land, our people of about 35 million people,

our sacred Uzbekistan is the only one. His land is dear and precious. The independence of the country is an inestimable gift. That's why we celebrate Independence Day, which is the greatest and dearest day for us. It has become a noble tradition in our country to welcome people with deep preparation.

My homeland is Uzbekistan. I live in Uzbekistan. I am very proud to live in such a prosperous country. My country is a country of great scientists and sages. We would not be mistaken if we say that the aspirations and dreams of our great ancestors, in general, our great grandfathers, who founded the First and Second Renaissance periods in our national history, are embodied in the idea of "New Uzbekistan". The history of mankind shows that, the processes of spiritual awakening in the life of any people lead to the realization of national identity and raise the country's economic and cultural development to a new level. If the goal is clear, the great and good intentions we have set will be realized, and the results of our actions will not simply remain unanswered. Today, Uzbekistan is becoming a country of democratic changes, wide opportunities and practical work. This process is the biggest result of our reforms for us. Because the clarity of the goal is the most important criterion that ensures the effectiveness of actions and aspirations. Building a new Uzbekistan is not just people's dreams, but the more clearly the goal is set, the more difficult it is to achieve it, and the achieved result is considered to be an incomparable happiness. Of course, we were all pleased with the results achieved in a short period of time due to the reforms. The main goal of these results is the permanence of our independence, the safety of our people, the purity of our sky, the establishment of a great and powerful society, the rise and creation, always striving towards the goals, not just being a spectator, but showing our power to the world. . Only then will the country's rise, prosperity and more rapid growth increase.

Of course, it is no secret to anyone that many problems remained unsolved before independence, and that not living a peaceful life was experienced by everyone. The solution to these problems is clear and consistent after

independence we responded. In other words, our peace and independence are definitely in the hands of each person. Especially “human rights and freedoms”, “rule of law”,

“openness and transparency”, “freedom of speech”, “freedom of religion and belief”, “public control”, “inviolability of private property” throughout our country strengthened. In a word, problems and inconveniences among the population have been solved after independence. Since then, growth and development have always been with us, with the people, and with our Motherland. After independence, we openly recognized the existence of problems related to forced labor, especially child labor, unemployment, poverty, corruption, housing, education and medicine, and solved them together with our general public.

We must openly admit one fact: the reform processes are expanding more and more over time, and the intense times are setting more and more important tasks in front of us. Life itself teaches us many things. That’s why we’re always on the lookout. Where there is research, it is natural that along with achievements, there are shortcomings and defects. But since we are children of Uzbekistan, simple shortcomings and defects do not matter to our growth, that is, nothing can hinder our development. As the honorable President said, “Rising will never be easy”. We never stop growing, we are constantly moving. The role of young people in creating a new enlightened society of Uzbekistan is very incomparable. Today, young people are waking up, our society is waking up. A spiritually awake society is, without a doubt, a powerful force. New Uzbekistan means, first of all, new: economic relations, a new economic outlook. One of my personal contributions to the creation of an enlightened society is that in 2020-2021, I took the proud 1st place in the district and regional stages of the Science Olympiad and became a participant in the republican stage. As a creative girl, my poems were published, and for the first time my book “The First Step to the Goal” was published. I finished the school with excellent grades, I earned the title of “Student” by justifying the trust given to me by the gold medalist and my teachers. Several of

my poems were published in the poetry book “Surkhan’s Young Tenants”. In 2022, I was found worthy of the “Provincial Governor’s Scholarship”. These achievements of mine are the result of my noble goals and aspirations set not only for myself, but also for my country. I think that the achievements of each generation should stand tall in front of their homeland, that they are children of Uzbekistan who have made their contribution. As it is never easy to rise, it is not easy to be the owner of achievements. I have been achieving my goals and dreams because my friend is a book. As a student, one of the goals I set for myself is to continue my studies and contribute to my country by working on myself in the field of journalism, I will achieve my goals and I am always on the move. It can be understood from the words of the Honorable President that “I want to say frankly: my nature absolutely cannot accept such a fake life. Our people trusted me, justifying this high trust, creating decent living conditions for our country is the meaning of my life. As I am responsible for the fate of millions of people, I cannot do anything else regarding the reforms, I cannot leave everything as it was before”. So, our head of state always tries to rise together with us, always supports his people, the peace and tranquility of our people is happiness for our head of state. We, the youth of Uzbekistan, always work shoulder to shoulder with our head of state and contribute to the development of our country.

In conclusion, we will certainly try to make our own incomparable contribution to the creation of an enlightened society of the youth of Uzbekistan. Because our ancestors endured unparalleled suffering and left us this independent land after fighting for freedom, we must leave our country to our descendants in a more beautiful way. I believe that the great blessing of our independence is considered sacred for young people like us, and it is the duty of every child of Uzbekistan to honor it. The fact that the Independence Day is widely celebrated by our people as the dearest and greatest holiday in our country shows that it is a shining example of peace, peaceful life and stability in our motherland.

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